

Improved urban land cover mapping using WorldView-2 imagery, for estimating the geographical distribution of the available roof surface area for photovoltaic potential applications in urban environments.

Aikaterini Stamou ^{a,*}, Petros Patias ^b, Maria Tsakiri-Strati ^b, Olga Georgoula ^b

^aDr. Eng., Research Fellow, Faculty of Rural and Surveying Engineering, Department of Cadastre, Photogrammetry and Cartography,

^a Professor, Faculty of Rural and Surveying Engineering, Department of Cadastre, Photogrammetry and Cartography,
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

*Corresponding author: astamoy@topo.auth.gr, +302310996407

Abstract: This paper presents an object-oriented approach for analyzing and characterizing the urban landscape structure at building level, using high-resolution satellite imagery of WorldView-2. More specifically, this study aims at extracting building information such as area, rooftop surface materials, for estimating the potential of photovoltaic (PV) applications in the available building stock of the examined area. The study area is the city of Kalamaria in Greece. With the applied methodology, the 8-band multispectral imagery of WorldView-2 is used for object-oriented feature extraction techniques, using the additional multispectral bands of the image (Coastal Blue, Red Edge Yellow, NIR-2). Normalized Difference Indexes and rules, using the available band information, were used in the classification hierarchy in order to facilitate object segmentation and obtain greater classification accuracy. The extracted information of the building stock is then introduced in a GIS environment for further processing. Continuously, an hierarchical methodology is introduced to compute the physical, geographical and technical limits of PV applications in roofs. The applied method and the geographical distribution of the derived data can prove to be an effective tool for policy makers, so as to determine the potentials that an urban environment has, regarding its bioclimatic upgrade.

Keywords: Remote Sensing, Geographical Information Science and Systems, Geography and Sustainable Development, Land Cover/Land Use

1. Introduction

The contemporary urban environments are more and more characterized by their densely built up areas, the excessive use of building materials that are harmful for the environment and the climate's quality, the observed congestion due to massive use of cars and the consequent emission of gas that leads to air pollution and climate change. At the same time, the organized green spaces occupy limited extent considering the urban scale. For all these reasons, the continuous evolution of the urban forms does not correspond to a sustainable development which respects the environment through time.

It is therefore obvious that the need for managing environmental issues of an urban tissue, as well as the need for its bioclimatic upgrade is more than necessary. In order to achieve these goals, it is necessary to study and analyze all processes that take place inside an urban environment, and at the same time to analyze and foresee future situations that will occur in it.

This paper presents an object-oriented approach for analyzing and characterizing the urban landscape structure at building level, in order to provide a different approach for estimating the potential of photovoltaic (PV) applications inside an urban environment.

2. Study area and data

The study area for this case study is the city of Kalamaria in Greece. Kalamaria is a typical Mediterranean city, in the North part of Greece that ideally includes both old and new built-up areas, with high and low built-up density respectively.

The available high-resolution satellite imagery of WorldView-2 that cover the urban complex of the city of Kalamaria, have acquisition date of February, 21, 2010. The images were already orthorectified by DigitalGlobe and were provided to the authors after successful participation in the 8-band research challenge of DigitalGlobe in 2010. WorldView-2, launched October 2009, is the first high-resolution 8-band multispectral commercial satellite. The additional multispectral bands of the image (Coastal Blue, Red Edge Yellow, NIR-2) are expected to increase the accuracy of feature extraction techniques.

3. Methodology

In order to achieve the goals of this study, a stratified methodology was conducted:

1) The first step was the necessary pre-processing of the available images. This included image fusion techniques, since the provided images of the study area were one panchromatic image with spatial resolution 0.5m and one multispectral image with spatial resolution 2m. Both PCA and Gram-Schmidt techniques were applied in order to produce the desired fused image that will maintain the spectral characteristics of the initial multispectral image as well as the high spatial resolution of the initial panchromatic image. (Klonus and Ehlers 2009; Stamou 2013). The evaluation of these two techniques, based on statistical tests and indices as well as the visual interpretation of the images, revealed that the PCA fused image has maintained better the valuable spectral and spatial information of the initial imagery.

2) The following procedure was the application of image classification techniques. In detail, a rule-based object-oriented classification procedure was applied. Object-oriented classification provides a variety of additional parameters for classifying high resolution remotely sensed imagery in urban areas. According to this method, spatial information such as texture, shape, and context can be used both to increase the discrimination between spectrally similar urban land cover types. (Dengsheng et al., 2010)

In this study, the multi-resolution segmentation approach was used. All pixels are initialized as single segments that are merged as the algorithm progresses. The algorithm of this clustering process is based on the homogeneity in color and shape of the neighbouring image objects. (Stamou et al., 2012) Normalized Difference Indexes and rules, using the available band information, were used in the classification hierarchy in order to facilitate object segmentation and obtain greater classification accuracy. The classification process was conducted in e-Cognition Software and six object classes were distinguished: (1) buildings with tiled-roofs, (2) buildings with cemented-roofs, (3) buildings with bright roofs, (4) vegetation, (5) roads and (6) shadow. (Fig.1)

Figure 1. Detail of the final classified image of the study area, with the six object classes

3) The extraction of building stock of the study area was the next step. The object classes of three building types, that were identified from the classification process, were transformed to shapefiles and then introduced in a GIS environment for further processing. With the concession that the footprint of the buildings depicts also the rooftop area, a geodatabase of the study area containing information about the building stock was conducted. More specifically, this geodatabase includes information about the geographical distribution for every single building of the study area (x and y coordinates), the area in m² for every rooftop, as well as the surface material of the rooftop. The final geodatabase had more than 5000 records. (Fig.2)

Figure 2. The produced geodatabase of the building stock includes information about location, area and roof type material; example for one building in the study area

4) The final step was the calculation of the useful roof-top area for PV applications. An hierarchical methodology was introduced to compute the physical, geographical and technical limits of PV applications in roofs, since limitations such as orientation, location, shading and other existing uses in roofs, determine the relation between initial roof surface area (in this case roof area that was extracted from the satellite image) and the final roof-top available area for PV applications. Four reduction factors were calculated in order to derive the available roof area:

a. Depending on the surface material and the orientation of the roof: it is considered that only areas with South or South-East orientation are usable for PV applications. If one building has cemented roof or bright roof, it was assumed that the roof surface is flat, and the whole area is usable:

$$f_{\text{cemented/bright roofs}} = 1$$

If one building has tiled roof, only half of the surface will have the desirable orientation:

$$f_{\text{tiled roofs}} = 1/2$$

b. A reduction factor was introduced based on calculations of shading effects in the study area (Stamou 2013): $f_{\text{shading}} = 0.5$

c. Finally a reduction factor was introduced due to other uses that might occur in the building roofs, based on bibliography (Wiginton et al., 2011): $f_{\text{other uses}} = 0.78$

With this procedure, from the initial roof area A_i for every building, the usable for PV roof area A_{PV} was calculated, for the whole study area:

$$A_{PVi} = A_i * f_{\text{cemented/bright/tiled roofs}} * f_{\text{shading}} * f_{\text{other uses}} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$A_{PV} = \sum A_{PVi} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

The advantages of this proposed methodology are multiple: in terms of time, this method can identify directly the geographical location of buildings with ideal conditions for PV applications (depending on area, roof type, shading and orientation). In terms of accuracy, this method can estimate with very good approximation the usable roof surface for PV, and finally in terms of money saving, this method does not need in situ measurements that are time-consuming and not at all cost-effective.

4. Conclusions

The proposed method, using the available building stock of the study area, is based absolutely on the derived features of the satellite image. This constitutes an innovative and effective approach to the evaluation of the potentials that has the urban environment, regarding its bioclimatic upgrade. With the applied method, the available roof surface area for large-scale photovoltaic development is estimated, introducing an effective way of calculating this kind of data, for which no direct data exists. The potential annual energy production can also be calculated, demonstrating the effectiveness, as well as the new potentials that arise from remote sensing applications.

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